

I-RIM 3D 2025 - Workshop Proposal

How Continual Learning and Generative AI are transforming Robotics

Organizers:

Enrico Donato*, Scuola Superiore Sant'Anna, Pisa, enrico.donato@santannapisa.it

Vincenzo Lomonaco, Università di Pisa, Pisa, vincenzo.lomonaco@unipi.it

Egidio Falotico, Scuola Superiore Sant'Anna, Pisa, egidio.falotico@santannapisa.it

* corresponding organizer

1. Workshop Format

The workshop will feature invited talks and an open discussion, a pitch and a poster sessions for selected abstracts.

2. Workshop Objectives and Main Topics

Continual Learning (CL) and **Generative AI** (GenAI) are reshaping the future of intelligent systems. CL enables robots to adapt continuously to changing environments without forgetting but transferring prior knowledge, while GenAI - through large language and vision models, and generative models as contrastive and diffusion - unlocks new capabilities in perception, reasoning, and behaviour generation. Together, these approaches promise **long-term autonomy**, **adaptability**, and **scalable intelligence** for real-world robotics. However, integrating CL and GenAI into robotic systems remains challenging due to issues such as real-time constraints, embodiment, safety, and transferring models from simulation to physical platforms.

This workshop aims to connect the Artificial Intelligence and Robotics communities to:

- identify open challenges in deploying CL and GenAI in robotics;
- share recent algorithmic and systems-level innovations;
- showcase real-world applications of adaptive and generative robotic systems;
- promote reproducible benchmarks and cross-disciplinary collaboration.

Main topics include:

- **Continual Learning Algorithms:** Online learning, memory systems, and reinforcement learning for resource-constrained robots.
- **Generative Models in Robotics:** Use of LLMs, generative models, and VLMs for planning, control, and interaction.
- **Evaluation and Safety:** Benchmarks for continual and generative learning, domain shifts, uncertainty, and robustness.
- **Real-World Applications:** Deployment in service, industrial, assistive, and field robotics where adaptation is essential.

3. Keywords

Continual Learning, Generative AI, Robotics, Lifelong Learning, Online Learning, Foundation Models, Large Language Models, Adaptive Systems, Embodied AI

4. Preferred Date

October 17th, 2025

Workshop organizers and confirmed invited speakers can guarantee their presence only on that day, because of other incoming academic events.

5. List of Speakers

- Dr. Vincenzo Lomonaco (Università di Pisa) *Confirmed*
Title: *The Future of Continual Learning in the Era of Foundation Models: Three Key Directions*
- Prof. Matteo Saveriano (Università di Trento) *Confirmed*
Title: *Towards Safe Continual Learning from Demonstration*

- Dr. Egidio Falotico (Scuola Superiore Sant’Anna) *Confirmed*
Title: *Continual Learning and Generative AI in Soft Robotics*
- Prof. Tatiana Tommasi (Politecnico di Torino) *Confirmed*
Title: *Generative AI for Robot Grasping*
- Prof. Loris Roveda (Politecnico di Milano) *Confirmed*
Title: *Unleashing Autonomy for Real-World Robots*

6. Expected Number of Attendees

We anticipate approximately 30+ participants with expertise or interest in Robotics and Artificial Intelligence.

7. Target Audience

This workshop targets researchers, engineers, and practitioners from both academia and industry working at the intersection of Artificial Intelligence and Robotics. It is particularly relevant for those developing adaptive robotic systems, focusing on continual learning and generative AI, real-world deployment, safety, and long-term autonomy. The event also welcomes students and early-career researchers interested in these topics.

8. Workshop Outcomes

The workshop aims to foster collaboration between the two communities and establish a foundation for ongoing interdisciplinary exchange, from a national to an international viewspan. Expected outcomes:

- *presentation slides* and *poster materials* shared via the workshop webpage;
- a *summary report* highlighting key discussions, challenges, and future directions;
- *follow-up activities* such as collaborative projects or community-driven benchmark proposals.

9. Plan for Special Issue or Session

We plan to propose a *special issue* in a journal relevant to the I-RIM community (e.g., IEEE Robotics and Autonomous Systems or IEEE Computational Intelligence related journals, Frontiers in Robotics and AI) focused on Continual Learning and Generative AI for Robotics. Workshop speakers and contributors will be invited to submit extended versions of their work. The special issue will encourage submissions that emphasize real-world deployment, empirical evaluation, and interdisciplinary collaboration. Additionally, a *focus paper* on this topic on a high-impact journal is programmed, highlighting key challenges and future directions on this intersection.

10. Call for Extended Abstracts

We will issue a call for extended abstracts (2–4 pages) on relevant topics (e.g. continual robotics learning, generative models for robotics, machine learning for robotics). Submissions will be peer-reviewed by the organizing committee. Selected contributions will be invited to present a short pitch and present a poster during the workshop poster session. The call will be disseminated through academic mailing lists (e.g., I-RIM, academic institutions), social media, and the workshop webpage. Submissions will be handled via a simple platform (e.g., Google Forms). Important dates and instructions will be provided on the workshop webpage.

11. Workshop Webpage

The workshop webpage is currently *under development* and will be hosted as a page of the BRAIR Lab website: <https://www.santannapisa.it/en/institute/biorobotics/brair-lab>. The page will include the program, speaker details, call for abstracts, submission instructions, and relevant updates. The BRAIR Lab website already includes an example from a previous workshop.

12. Notes on Registration

We plan to use the two free one-day registrations to cover the participation of confirmed invited speakers who are not otherwise funded. Additional speakers and attendees will register through the standard I-RIM process, supported by their own funds. We will clearly communicate the registration procedure to all contributors and manage coordination to ensure smooth participation logistics.